

Appendix A: INT and CTR samples additional material

The additional material in this appendix comprises the complementary images and spectra of the INT sample presented in Figs. A.1 and A.2. Furthermore, the following pages present tables of the INT and CTR samples. Table A.1 shows the information of the initial interacting candidates selected from the [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog. Table A.2 presents the confirmed INT galaxies radial velocities and their corresponding CTR galaxies selected from the SDSS. Tables A.3 and A.4 show the fluxes of the INT sample forbidden and permitted emission lines, respectively. Tables A.5 and A.6 present the same for the CTR sample. Finally, Tables A.7 and A.8 present the classifications with different diagnostic diagrams for the INT and CTR samples, respectively.

Fig. A.1. Same as in Fig. 1, but for the INT galaxies not included there.

Fig. A.1. continued.

Fig. A.2. Same as in Fig. 2, but for the INT galaxies not included there.

Fig. A.2. continued.

Fig. A.2. continued.

Table A.1. Interacting galaxies sample selected from the Arp & Madore Catalogue.

System Name (1)	Component (2)	α (2000) (hh:mm:ss)	δ (2000) (dd:mm:ss)	PA [°] (3)	Systemic velocity [km/s] (4)
AM 0012-235	A = LEDA 73318	00:15:10.230	-23:42:58.50	195.5	19076
	B = 2MASX J00150913-2343541				>30000
AM 0103-520	A = ESO 195-30	01:05:51.320	-51:45:04.50	58/197	-
	B = LEDA 452921				-
	C = Gaia DR3 4927464765788769536/ ESO 195-IG 030 NED02				-
AM 0237-525	A = LEDA 128584	02:38:44.420	-52:46:39.10	220	-
	B = [MDS99] F154-017 LSBG F154-017				-
AM 0302-611	G1 = ESO 116-6	03:03:30.430	-61:08:19.50	252/320	-
	G2 = ESO 116-IG 006 NED02				-
	G3 = 2MASX J03033046-6108201				-
	G4 = 2MASX J03032756-6108281				8553
AM 0305-824	A = LEDA 222825	03:01:44.9	-82:35:31	328	-
AM 0338-320	A = 6dFGS gJ034029.8-315142	03:40:29.660	-31:51:41.30	237	-
	B = 2MASX J03402854-3151520				-
AM 0348-502	G1 = ESO 201-4	03:50:22.910	-50:18:09.00	343/305.5	10766
	G2 = 2MASX J03502377-5018354				10940
	G3 = 2MASX J03501198-5017165				-
AM 0737-764	A = ESO 35-11	07:35:18.700	-76:54:52.09	200.5	5900
	B = WISEA J073520.20-765437.6				-
AM 0830-235	A = ESO 495-16	08:32:41.1	-24:02:32	159	7924
	B = LEDA 86223				-
AM 0908-674	A = NGC 2788	09:09:03.394	-67:55:59.61	294	1641
AM 0952-273	A = LEDA 749047	09:54:56.750	-27:50:50.90	330	-
	B = LEDA 181883				-
AM 1026-442	G1 - A = NGC 3261	10:29:01.263	-44:39:27.03	3	2563
AM 1058-243	A = LEDA 784699	11:00:50.060	-24:55:07.89	276	22917
	B = WISEA J110049.40-245506.4				-
AM 1125-374	A = LEDA 615154	11:27:36.207	-37:57:18.13	289.45	17392
	B = 2MASX J11273693-3757208				-
AM 1132-450	A = ESO 266-5	11:35:09.287	-45:23:15.97	165.7	5266
	B = LEDA 35805				-
AM 1228-260	A = ESO 506-15	12:31:16.842	-26:17:29.93	2.9	5912
	B = WISE J123116.76-261741.1/ AM 1228-260 NED01				-
AM 1238-340	A = LEDA 88654	12:40:41.124	-34:21:47.75	245	16247
	B = 2MASS J12404057-3421489				-
AM 1411-434	A = IC 4386	14:15:02.475	-43:57:39.94	184	1882
	B = IC 4387				-
AM 1438-400	G1 = ESO 327-8	14:41:20.089	-40:19:50.69	180	7825
	G2 = WISEA J144118.20-401956.4			202	-
AM 1445-274	G1 = ESO 448-2	14:48:52.770	-27:52:38.17	51.7	14292
	G2 = WISEA J144852.47-275242.2				-
AM 1722-595	A = ESO 138-27	17:26:43.352	-59:55:55.17	234.3	6230
	B = LEDA 367658				-
AM 1933-422	G1 = NGC 6806	19:37:05.0	-42:17:47	119.3	5733
	G2 = 2MASX J19372362-4218194			98.8	-
	G3 = LEDA 3098348				5996
AM 1941-564	A = IC 4890	19:45:34.844	-56:33:04.92	193.4	5239
	B = WISEA J194534.04-563334.2				-
AM 2004-662	G1 = NAME McL A/ ESO 105-G026	20:09:27.332	-66:12:55.63	127.6	11299
	G2 = WISEA J200937.54-661343.8				-
	G3 = NAME McL B/ ESO 105-G026			96.3	-

Notes. (1) System name according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalogue. (2) Galaxy identifier from Simbad (and NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database - NED in case of divergency) when available. (3) Position angle of the observed slits. (4) NED systemic velocities for the galaxies with previous information.

Table A.1. continued.

System Name (1)	Component (2)	$\alpha(2000)$ (hh:mm:ss)	$\delta(2000)$ (dd:mm:ss)	PA [°] (3)	Systemic velocity [km/s] (4)
	WISEA J200924.36-661241.8				
AM 2024-525	G4 = LEDA 306574				-
	G1 = ESO 186-51	20:28:16.548	-52:40:32.00	215.8	4912
	G3 = LEDA 64756				-
	G2 = 2MASX J20281941-5240587			283.5	16084
	G4 = LEDA 440336				-
	WISEA J202809.53-524037.6				
AM 2031-500	A = ESO 234-49	20:35:20.907	-49:51:15.29	41	2579
	B = LEDA 65018				4561
AM 2036-510	G1 = FRL 908	20:40:03.800	-50:55:51.19	145.7	-
	G2 = ESO 234-62				4800
	G3 = 2MASS J20401226-5057017				-
AM 2037-550	A = ESO 187-1	20:41:27.90	-54:58:47.3	70	11446
AM 2038-323	G1 = NGC 6947	20:41:12.795	-32:30:13.22	24.8	5592
	G2 = LEDA 690531/ WISEA J204110.83-323106.8				37171
AM 2057-650	A = ESO 107-2	21:01:17.64	-64:57:53.0	108.7	13720
	B = LEDA 317523				-
AM 2100-503	G1 = ESO 235-45	21:03:48.159	-50:21:52.19	289.4	4934
	G2 = 6dFGS gJ210341.7-502203			69	15233
	G3 = WISEA J210346.19-502146.2				
AM 2106-624	G1 = ESO 107-9	21:10:06.84	-62:35:52.5	63.5	15761
	G2 = 2MASX J21101120-6235442				-
AM 2108-452	G1 = 2dFGRS TGS876Z088	21:11:34.35	-45:15:08.0	137,113.1,112.5	-
	G2 = ESO 286-73				9569
	G3 = LEDA 528634				-
	LCRS B210819.1-452815				
AM 2117-371	G1 = 6dFGS gJ212026.9-370005	21:20:27.514	-37:00:04.88	274	
	APMUKS(BJ) B211720.70-371250.1				
	G2 = 6dFGS gJ212028.1-370005				31109
AM 2117-515	G1 - A = ESO 236-IG 005 NED01	21:21:14.09	-51:43:57.7	83	15471
	G2 - B = ESO 236-IG 005 NED02			5	-
	G3 - E = ESO 236-IG 005 NED03			285.5	-
	G4 - C = 2MASS J21211536-5143581			83	-
	G5 = 2MASS J21211361-5143535/ (tadpole at NW of G3)			285.5	-
	G6 - D = LEDA 453396			5	-
	knots (See Fig. 1)			285.5	-
AM 2117-682	G1 = LEDA 127236	21:21:38.623	-68:10:05.06	273.8	25987
	G2 = 2MASS J21215262-6810066				-
	G3 = LEDA 287882				-
AM 2132-664	G1 - A = ESO 107-38	21:36:24.618	-66:28:50.10	175.5	8490
	G2 = 2MASS J21362448-6628496 (Our images show that it is a star).				-
	G3 - B = LEDA 304337				-
AM 2137-515	A = ESO 236-31	21:41:17.04	-51:45:48.2	209	16765
	B = LEDA 453034				-
	WISEA J214120.56-514450.9				
AM 2147-544	G1 = ESO 189-5	21:50:58.202	-54:33:08.56	229	8623
	G2 = LEDA 190556	21:51:00.125	-54:33:37.35		-
AM 2217-490	G1 = ESO 238-2	22:20:46.258	-48:45:17.43	143.2	9212
	G2 = 2MASX J22204151-4844140				9060
	G3 = LEDA 484571/ GALEXASC J222040.91-484242.0				9081
AM 2220-493	G1 = ESO 238-6	22:23:13.043	-49:17:25.78	168	-
	G2 = LEDA 95417				17946
AM 2220-661	A = LEDA 127657	22:24:14.320	-66:02:15.70	75	10556

Notes. (1) System name according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalogue. (2) Galaxy identifier from Simbad (and NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database - NED in case of divergency) when available. (3) Position angle of the observed slits. (4) NED systemic velocities for the galaxies with previous information.

Table A.1. continued.

System Name (1)	Component (2)	$\alpha(2000)$ (hh:mm:ss)	$\delta(2000)$ (dd:mm:ss)	PA [°] (3)	Systemic velocity [km/s] (4)
AM 2246-490	G1 = ESO 239-2 G2 = LEDA 482697/ PRC D-41	22:49:40.219	-48:51:01.92	322	12901 -

Notes. (1) System name according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalogue. (2) Galaxy identifier from Simbad (and NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database - NED in case of divergency) when available. (3) Position angle of the observed slits. (4) NED systemic velocities for the galaxies with previous information.

Table A.2. Confirmed INT pairs and groups radial velocities and information of their CTR galaxies.

System name (1)	Radial velocity [km/s] (2)	SDSS DR9 Plate-MJd-Fiberid (3)	CTR galaxy name (4)
AM 0012-235 A	18961 ± 92	2124-53770-0272	2MASX J14030448+2446252
B	18830 ± 95	2613-54481-0304	2MASX J12340843+1929256
AM 0103-520 ^(II) A	16345 ± 83	1693-53446-0629	2MASX J17053367+2506193
B	16441 ± 65	1601-53115-0280	LEDA 1389965
AM 0302-611 G1 (A)	8321 ± 97	2746-54232-0165	UGC 9185
G2 (D)	8509 ± 129	-	-
G3 (C)	8543 ± 54	1237663234989424850 ^(*) (SDSS ObjId, no spectrum)	UGC 29
G4 (B)	8419 ± 83	2776-54554-0098	2MASX J14451344+1745338
AM 0338-320 A	29034 ± 102	0420-51871-0517	2MASX J00550203+1516012
B	29116 ± 179	0421-51821-0003	2MASX J01035856+1346065
AM 0348-502 G1 (A)	10707 ± 54	2774-54534-0448	IC 1021
G2 (B)	10759 ± 63	1607-53083-0452	LEDA 3090857
G3 (C)	10581 ± 116	1652-53555-0578	KISS F1530-273/WISEA J153423.63+295110.4
AM 0737-764 A	5899 ± 35	2352-53770-0006	NGC 3327
B	5875 ± 33	2515-54180-0046	LEDA 1557424
AM 0830-235 A	7838 ± 92	2234-53823-0120	NGC 4514
B	7628 ± 95	2130-53881-0553	2MASX J14230749+2835418
AM 1058-243 A	22782 ± 100	1937-53388-0453	LEDA 1853840
B	22881 ± 42	0731-52460-0345	LEDA 1396403
AM 1125-374 A	17075 ± 30	1771-53498-0483	2MASX J12593825+1510458
B	16851 ± 26	1588-52965-0534	LEDA 1847759
AM 1132-450 A	5226 ± 85	2132-53493-0224	IC 1006
B	5078 ± 63	2277-53705-0378	UGC 4504
AM 1228-260 A	5737 ± 83	1852-53534-0298	NVSS J160707+220337
B	5835 ± 76	-	-
AM 1238-340 A	15961 ± 94	1693-53446-0629	2MASX J17053367+2506193
B	16255 ± 82	-	-
AM 1411-434 A	1877 ± 45	1237680245198487603 ^(*) (SDSS ObjId, no SDSS spectrum)	NGC 7497
B	1788 ± 38	2273-53709-27	UGC 4444
AM 1445-274 G1 (A)	14008 ± 83	2170-53875-0347	Z 107-41
G2 (B)	13847 ± 91	-	-
AM 1722-595 A	6119 ± 60	1929-53349-0372	IC 509
B	6162 ± 69	-	-
AM 1933-422 G1 (A)	5562 ± 128	0275-51910-0320	NGC 3339
G2 (B)	5582 ± 139	1776-53858-0098	LEDA 1429669
G3 (C)	5609 ± 84	2580-54092-0232	MCG+02-25-009
AM 1941-564 A	5130 ± 86	2350-53765-0539	NGC 3204
B	4787 ± 91	-	-
AM 2004-662 ^(III) A (G1)	11100 ± 220	2426-53795-0583	LEDA 1427577
B (G3)	10876 ± 101	-	-
AM 2036-510 G2 (A)	11792 ± 48	2523-54572-0428	LEDA 1390992
G1 (B)	12224 ± 92	1266-52709-0142	SDSS J081524.39+254729.7
G3 (C)	12018 ± 90	-	-
AM 2106-624 ^(III) G1 (A)	15761 ± 44	2759-54534-0160	IC 4410
G2 (B)	15382 ± 71	2227-53820-0018	LEDA 1785836
AM 2108-452 G2 (A)	9400 ± 77	2782-54592-0240	LEDA 1468533
G1 (B)	9633 ± 28	2126-53794-0075	2MASX J14164251+2854406
G3 (C)	9436 ± 50	0420-51871-0285	SDSS J004923.00+135600.9
AM 2117-515 G1 (A)	15053 ± 103	0860-52319-0120	LEDA 1866838
G2 (B)	15443 ± 178	2268-53682-0424	LEDA 1448216
G4 (C)	15293 ± 104	-	-
G5 (D)	15535 ± 56	-	-
G6 (E)	15396 ± 18	2765-54535-0129	2MASX J15065663+1426145
Central Knots	15305 ± 123	-	-
AM 2132-664 ^(IV) G1 (A)	8469 ± 130	2094-53851-0261	MCG+05-32-055
G3 (B)	8222 ± 43	-	-
AM 2217-490 ^(V) G1 (A)	9092 ± 57	2496-54178-0330	Z 126-20
G2 (B)	9003 ± 102	2599-54234-0571	IC 3615
AM 2220-493 G1 (A)	17832 ± 101	2764-54535-0355	MCG+03-38-035
G2 (B)	17746 ± 43	2518-54243-0066	2MASX J15503870+1530524

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog and [Table A.1](#). (2) Systemic velocity obtained following the method described in [Sect. 2.2](#). (3) Corresponding SDSS DR9 control partner. (4) Control galaxy identifier from Simbad (and NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database - NED in case of divergency) when available. ^(II) AM 0103-520: C is not a member of the system. ^(III) AM 2004-662: G2 and G4 are foreground galaxies. ^(III) AM 2106-624: A = ESO107-009 is a member with radial velocity 15761 ± 44 km/s ([Strauss et al. 1992](#)), but we do not have the source spectra, because the slit was centered on a star. The A component CTR galaxy was not included in the next comparisons since we do not observe component G1. C (indicated in [Fig. A.1](#)) could be a member; however, it was not observed. ^(IV) AM 2132-664: Component G2 it is a star. ^(V) AM 2217-490: G3 (6dFJ2220410) is a member but was not observed. There is also a possible member toward the east of G1 (not in the image of [Fig. A.1](#)). ^(*) The control galaxy is not included in the INT versus CTR sample comparison as the spectrum of the control is unavailable in the SDSS DR9.

Table A.3. continued.

Object	[O II] λ 3726 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[O II] λ 3729 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[O III] λ 4363 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[O III] λ 4959 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[O III] λ 5007 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[N II] λ 5755 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	He I λ 5876 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[O I] λ 6300 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[N II] λ 6548 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[N II] λ 6583 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[S II] λ 6716 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	[S II] λ 6731 flux x 10^{-15} [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]
AM2117-515 G5	22.57 $\pm$ 0.32	19.95 $\pm$ 0.28	0.13 $\pm$ 0.04	18.42 $\pm$ 0.17	54.62 $\pm$ 0.44	-	1.22 $\pm$ 0.05	0.48 $\pm$ 0.02	0.99 $\pm$ 0.03	2.58 $\pm$ 0.1	3.09 $\pm$ 0.04	1.88 $\pm$ 0.05
AM2117-515 G6	7.93 $\pm$ 1.48	15.53 $\pm$ 1.36	-	-	2.02 $\pm$ 0.08	0.17 $\pm$ 0.02	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.28 $\pm$ 0.02	1.06 $\pm$ 0.07	6.49 $\pm$ 0.13	3.64 $\pm$ 0.12	2.45 $\pm$ 0.06
AM2117-515 KNOTS	5.57 $\pm$ 0.09	7.44 $\pm$ 0.11	-	1.57 $\pm$ 0.02	4.65 $\pm$ 0.05	0.01 $\pm$ 0.01	0.31 $\pm$ 0.02	0.15 $\pm$ 0.01	0.54 $\pm$ 0.01	1.97 $\pm$ 0.04	1.64 $\pm$ 0.02	1.16 $\pm$ 0.02
AM2132-664 G1	-	1118.5 $\pm$ 195.36	-	45.26 $\pm$ 4.25	214.86 $\pm$ 19.94	23.48 $\pm$ 2.19	18.27 $\pm$ 0.69	24.11 $\pm$ 2.1	160.98 $\pm$ 3.84	489.88 $\pm$ 3.33	57.75 $\pm$ 6.4	76.94 $\pm$ 4.1
AM2132-664 G3	10.85 $\pm$ 0.34	8.17 $\pm$ 0.37	-	1.08 $\pm$ 0.03	3.78 $\pm$ 0.04	0.31 $\pm$ 0.01	0.34 $\pm$ 0.06	0.28 $\pm$ 0.02	1.17 $\pm$ 0.11	2.85 $\pm$ 0.06	1.83 $\pm$ 0.03	1.4 $\pm$ 0.06
AM2217-490 G1	119.29 $\pm$ 1.38	86.34 $\pm$ 2.0	-	17.55 $\pm$ 0.19	54.88 $\pm$ 0.45	1.37 $\pm$ 0.07	2.57 $\pm$ 0.12	4.52 $\pm$ 0.21	31.39 $\pm$ 0.51	96.85 $\pm$ 0.5	25.56 $\pm$ 0.55	23.31 $\pm$ 0.32
AM2217-490 G2	4.31 $\pm$ 0.08	7.69 $\pm$ 0.1	-	0.32 $\pm$ 0.03	1.29 $\pm$ 0.06	0.12 $\pm$ 0.02	0.4 $\pm$ 0.02	0.03 $\pm$ 0.01	0.99 $\pm$ 0.07	3.7 $\pm$ 0.05	1.75 $\pm$ 0.03	1.33 $\pm$ 0.03
AM2220-493 G1	323.44 $\pm$ 111.18	307.94 $\pm$ 107.54	199.97 $\pm$ 8.83	313.74 $\pm$ 4.51	815.01 $\pm$ 18.33	1.36 $\pm$ 0.18	-	15.85 $\pm$ 0.57	93.82 $\pm$ 1.66	86.71 $\pm$ 1.61	25.3 $\pm$ 0.59	24.47 $\pm$ 0.38
AM2220-493 G2	15.04 $\pm$ 3.34	26.59 $\pm$ 3.07	-	30.26 $\pm$ 0.65	88.12 $\pm$ 1.12	0.49 $\pm$ 0.1	0.91 $\pm$ 0.13	3.24 $\pm$ 0.11	13.06 $\pm$ 0.13	35.43 $\pm$ 0.25	12.84 $\pm$ 0.31	10.37 $\pm$ 0.38

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalogue and [Table A.1](#).

Table A.4. Extinction corrected permitted emission lines measurements in the INT sample.

Object (1)	A_v [mag]	H δ flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	H γ flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	H β flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	H α flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$erg\ s^{-1}\ cm^{-2}$]	EW H α [$\text{\AA}$]
AM0012-235 A	-	-	-	-	-	0.7 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0012-235 B	-	-	-	-	-	1.0 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0103-520 A	3.1 $\pm$ 0.2	0.72 $\pm$ 0.11	0.57 $\pm$ 0.03	0.87 $\pm$ 0.07	2.49 $\pm$ 0.04	7.2 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0103-520 B	-	-	-	-	-	0.3 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0302-611 G1	5.6 $\pm$ 0.1	121.45 $\pm$ 5.04	59.88 $\pm$ 3.04	14.6 $\pm$ 0.61	41.9 $\pm$ 0.44	4.9 $\pm$ 0.0
AM0302-611 G2	1.8 $\pm$ 0.1	0.23 $\pm$ 0.05	0.69 $\pm$ 0.04	1.51 $\pm$ 0.06	4.32 $\pm$ 0.03	27.9 $\pm$ 0.2
AM0302-611 G3	-	-	-	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0
AM0302-611 G4	4.9 $\pm$ 0.4	-	-	3.54 $\pm$ 0.44	10.17 $\pm$ 0.79	1.8 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0338-320 A	1.8 $\pm$ 0.2	1.17 $\pm$ 0.13	2.33 $\pm$ 0.2	4.55 $\pm$ 0.36	13.06 $\pm$ 0.2	63.8 $\pm$ 0.4
AM0338-320 B	2.7 $\pm$ 0.2	0.5 $\pm$ 0.06	0.65 $\pm$ 0.05	0.8 $\pm$ 0.04	2.29 $\pm$ 0.05	11.0 $\pm$ 0.2
AM0348-502 G1	1.0 $\pm$ 0.2	0.19 $\pm$ 0.03	0.77 $\pm$ 0.04	1.48 $\pm$ 0.07	4.24 $\pm$ 0.03	9.2 $\pm$ 0.0
AM0348-502 G2	2.2 $\pm$ 0.1	3.68 $\pm$ 0.12	6.62 $\pm$ 0.25	15.24 $\pm$ 0.59	43.75 $\pm$ 0.25	81.4 $\pm$ 0.4
AM0348-502 G3	3.4 $\pm$ 0.2	2.32 $\pm$ 0.59	0.33 $\pm$ 0.1	1.49 $\pm$ 0.09	4.29 $\pm$ 0.04	11.0 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0737-764 A	2.9 $\pm$ 0.2	1.33 $\pm$ 0.62	6.27 $\pm$ 0.45	14.56 $\pm$ 0.64	41.78 $\pm$ 1.21	4.9 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0737-764 B	-	-	-	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0
AM0830-235 A	3.7 $\pm$ 0.1	-	7.15 $\pm$ 0.97	38.54 $\pm$ 1.34	110.6 $\pm$ 0.88	7.7 $\pm$ 0.1
AM0830-235 B	4.5 $\pm$ 0.2	-	-	5.72 $\pm$ 0.16	16.42 $\pm$ 1.02	1.0 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1058-243 A	3.7 $\pm$ 0.2	3.11 $\pm$ 0.39	7.59 $\pm$ 0.44	13.79 $\pm$ 1.01	39.57 $\pm$ 0.54	27.1 $\pm$ 0.2
AM1058-243 B	5.5 $\pm$ 0.3	52.9 $\pm$ 8.28	83.73 $\pm$ 9.39	95.81 $\pm$ 9.51	274.98 $\pm$ 6.05	75.4 $\pm$ 0.4
AM1125-374 A	4.0 $\pm$ 0.2	14.44 $\pm$ 1.95	10.66 $\pm$ 1.32	6.42 $\pm$ 0.25	18.44 $\pm$ 0.68	5.4 $\pm$ 0.2
AM1125-374 B	3.2 $\pm$ 0.2	1.75 $\pm$ 0.29	1.65 $\pm$ 0.26	1.13 $\pm$ 0.09	3.25 $\pm$ 0.06	4.0 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1132-450 A	4.0 $\pm$ 0.1	-	-	14.12 $\pm$ 0.5	40.52 $\pm$ 0.28	8.1 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1132-450 B	3.0 $\pm$ 0.1	3.1 $\pm$ 0.45	1.77 $\pm$ 0.54	8.38 $\pm$ 0.19	24.05 $\pm$ 0.09	21.9 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1228-260 A	3.1 $\pm$ 0.1	76.71 $\pm$ 6.83	146.0 $\pm$ 11.56	291.02 $\pm$ 12.9	835.22 $\pm$ 5.35	85.4 $\pm$ 0.4
AM1228-260 B	2.2 $\pm$ 0.1	7.58 $\pm$ 0.6	17.55 $\pm$ 0.9	38.67 $\pm$ 1.74	110.98 $\pm$ 0.86	382.3 $\pm$ 2.3
AM1238-340 A	3.0 $\pm$ 0.2	0.86 $\pm$ 0.13	3.59 $\pm$ 0.39	4.55 $\pm$ 0.22	13.07 $\pm$ 0.21	8.7 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1238-340 B	4.8 $\pm$ 0.1	-	11.5 $\pm$ 0.54	6.79 $\pm$ 0.32	19.49 $\pm$ 0.22	4.9 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1411-434 A	-	-	-	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0
AM1411-434 B	-	-	-	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0
AM1445-274 G1	4.2 $\pm$ 0.4	16.45 $\pm$ 1.83	-	13.36 $\pm$ 1.67	38.33 $\pm$ 1.62	10.6 $\pm$ 0.3
AM1445-274 G2	-	-	-	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0
AM1722-595 A	3.6 $\pm$ 0.1	123.72 $\pm$ 6.24	193.49 $\pm$ 7.79	401.2 $\pm$ 17.49	1151.44 $\pm$ 6.92	90.9 $\pm$ 0.4
AM1722-595 B	3.2 $\pm$ 0.1	-	2.06 $\pm$ 0.15	16.96 $\pm$ 0.57	48.66 $\pm$ 0.35	26.9 $\pm$ 0.2
AM1933-422 A	2.9 $\pm$ 0.1	57.96 $\pm$ 3.41	74.36 $\pm$ 3.03	201.02 $\pm$ 7.77	576.94 $\pm$ 3.2	85.5 $\pm$ 0.4
AM1933-422 B	2.2 $\pm$ 0.1	3.42 $\pm$ 0.13	1.47 $\pm$ 0.54	13.81 $\pm$ 0.34	39.64 $\pm$ 0.43	7.7 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1933-422 C	2.3 $\pm$ 0.1	6.13 $\pm$ 0.49	6.18 $\pm$ 0.35	13.55 $\pm$ 0.52	38.9 $\pm$ 0.24	35.3 $\pm$ 0.2
AM1941-564 A	5.2 $\pm$ 0.1	-	-	74.35 $\pm$ 2.53	213.38 $\pm$ 1.57	9.6 $\pm$ 0.1
AM1941-564 B	1.8 $\pm$ 0.3	-	-	0.51 $\pm$ 0.05	1.46 $\pm$ 0.1	1.1 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2004-662 G1	1.8 $\pm$ 0.1	1.76 $\pm$ 0.15	1.92 $\pm$ 0.06	4.34 $\pm$ 0.2	12.45 $\pm$ 0.07	22.8 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2004-662 G3	1.7 $\pm$ 0.4	0.11 $\pm$ 0.03	-	0.31 $\pm$ 0.03	0.88 $\pm$ 0.07	1.1 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2036-510 G1	1.4 $\pm$ 0.2	-	-	1.49 $\pm$ 0.02	4.27 $\pm$ 0.27	5.0 $\pm$ 0.3
AM2036-510 G2	2.1 $\pm$ 0.2	3.66 $\pm$ 0.16	5.83 $\pm$ 0.28	14.51 $\pm$ 0.72	41.64 $\pm$ 0.35	66.3 $\pm$ 0.4
AM2036-510 G3	2.7 $\pm$ 0.1	4.87 $\pm$ 0.45	8.19 $\pm$ 0.42	20.38 $\pm$ 0.85	58.48 $\pm$ 0.42	94.3 $\pm$ 0.6
AM2106-624 G2	7.4 $\pm$ 0.2	-	-	233.27 $\pm$ 13.23	669.48 $\pm$ 6.17	19.6 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2108-452 G1	2.4 $\pm$ 0.1	0.83 $\pm$ 0.2	2.22 $\pm$ 0.13	2.53 $\pm$ 0.09	7.27 $\pm$ 0.04	14.9 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2108-452 G2	-	-	-	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0
AM2108-452 G3	2.2 $\pm$ 0.1	0.67 $\pm$ 0.03	1.16 $\pm$ 0.08	1.65 $\pm$ 0.07	4.74 $\pm$ 0.04	40.7 $\pm$ 0.3
AM2117-515 G1	1.8 $\pm$ 0.1	-	0.22 $\pm$ 0.04	0.31 $\pm$ 0.01	0.88 $\pm$ 0.01	6.0 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2117-515 G2	2.4 $\pm$ 0.2	-	1.53 $\pm$ 0.19	4.86 $\pm$ 0.28	13.96 $\pm$ 0.13	43.3 $\pm$ 0.2
AM2117-515 G4	3.5 $\pm$ 0.1	6.24 $\pm$ 0.67	4.64 $\pm$ 0.37	6.07 $\pm$ 0.23	17.41 $\pm$ 0.1	35.0 $\pm$ 0.2
AM2117-515 G5	2.0 $\pm$ 0.1	1.92 $\pm$ 0.13	4.67 $\pm$ 0.27	11.02 $\pm$ 0.49	31.62 $\pm$ 0.4	280.2 $\pm$ 3.2
AM2117-515 G6	3.4 $\pm$ 0.2	1.72 $\pm$ 0.08	1.2 $\pm$ 0.04	6.77 $\pm$ 0.42	19.43 $\pm$ 0.21	39.7 $\pm$ 0.3
AM2117-515 KNOTS	1.4 $\pm$ 0.2	0.25 $\pm$ 0.02	1.2 $\pm$ 0.07	3.29 $\pm$ 0.19	9.45 $\pm$ 0.11	78.1 $\pm$ 0.7
AM2132-664 G1	6.2 $\pm$ 0.0	-	38.83 $\pm$ 13.17	281.77 $\pm$ 3.01	808.68 $\pm$ 3.78	15.3 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2132-664 G3	2.0 $\pm$ 0.2	0.74 $\pm$ 0.08	2.12 $\pm$ 0.17	3.87 $\pm$ 0.21	11.11 $\pm$ 0.09	29.3 $\pm$ 0.1
AM2217-490 G1	2.9 $\pm$ 0.1	16.33 $\pm$ 0.73	23.13 $\pm$ 0.77	53.93 $\pm$ 1.95	154.79 $\pm$ 0.78	47.3 $\pm$ 0.2
AM2217-490 G2	2.0 $\pm$ 0.1	1.17 $\pm$ 0.06	1.79 $\pm$ 0.06	3.92 $\pm$ 0.16	11.25 $\pm$ 0.07	33.2 $\pm$ 0.2
AM2220-493 G1	6.5 $\pm$ 0.2	-	157.94 $\pm$ 20.21	65.4 $\pm$ 3.77	187.69 $\pm$ 5.18	14.7 $\pm$ 0.4
AM2220-493 G2	3.7 $\pm$ 0.2	0.83 $\pm$ 0.06	4.55 $\pm$ 0.1	12.76 $\pm$ 0.62	36.62 $\pm$ 0.64	26.6 $\pm$ 0.4

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog and [Table A.1](#).

Table A.5. Extinction corrected emission lines measurements for forbidden and helium transitions in the CTR sample.

Object	[O III]λ3726 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[O III]λ3729 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[O III]λ4363 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[O III]λ4959 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[O III]λ5007 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[N III]λ5755 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	He Iλ5876 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[O I]λ6300 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[N II]λ6548 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[S II]λ6716 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	[S II]λ6731 flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]
0275-51910-0320	-	-	-	-	0.9±0.09	-	1.38±0.19	1.34±0.1	6.77±0.1	2.59±0.06	1.69±0.04
0420-51871-0285	1.39±0.63	3.86±0.86	-	0.09±0.05	0.7±0.05	-	-	-	0.29±0.06	0.39±0.14	0.32±0.08
0420-51871-0517	0.5±0.26	5.73±0.27	0.41±0.13	0.37±0.07	1.02±0.1	0.33±0.05	0.43±0.07	-	4.5±0.02	1.68±0.03	1.27±0.04
0421-51821-0003	-	7.34±3.57	-	1.63±0.73	1.71±0.64	0.63±0.22	-	-	3.07±1.02	0.51±0.21	0.54±0.2
0731-52460-0345	2.21±0.5	8.69±0.62	-	1.16±0.24	3.5±0.14	-	0.71±0.18	0.52±0.09	4.19±0.06	2.33±0.11	2.04±0.08
0860-52319-0120	0.71±0.16	6.35±0.19	-	0.2±0.06	0.75±0.04	-	0.38±0.11	0.2±0.06	3.37±0.02	1.6±0.01	1.2±0.01
1266-52709-0142	3.88±2.78	22.52±13.23	-	1.25±0.79	2.79±1.55	-	-	-	1.98±0.71	1.64±0.59	1.5±0.48
1588-52965-0534	0.46±0.13	0.71±0.06	-	-	0.16±0.06	0.19±0.02	0.06±0.02	0.09±0.04	0.62±0.02	0.34±0.02	0.25±0.01
1601-53115-0280	-	2.67±1.78	0.36±0.23	0.34±0.18	0.29±0.2	-	-	0.18±0.1	1.04±0.4	0.38±0.21	-
1607-53083-0452	18.72±2.32	96.25±2.68	1.22±0.27	5.2±0.27	17.33±0.56	1.33±0.31	2.16±0.65	5.37±0.57	74.02±1.29	21.86±0.34	17.81±0.15
1652-53555-0578	0.38±0.06	0.72±0.0	-	0.08±0.01	0.37±0.01	-	0.07±0.03	0.08±0.03	0.23±0.02	0.27±0.01	0.15±0.01
1693-53446-0629	-	1.54±0.19	-	0.1±0.03	0.37±0.11	-	0.39±0.14	-	0.5±0.05	0.49±0.03	0.32±0.05
1771-53498-0483	-	38.19±2.28	1.43±0.63	1.94±0.58	8.36±0.45	-	-	1.68±0.18	6.44±0.65	7.42±0.46	6.65±0.28
1776-53858-0098	2.45±0.85	5.12±0.21	0.06±0.05	0.08±0.03	0.75±0.06	1.25±0.38	0.5±0.11	0.21±0.1	0.36±0.01	0.83±0.01	0.51±0.02
1852-53534-0298	-	-	4.74±1.12	-	6.12±2.5	-	7.08±1.15	5.77±0.75	20.42±0.33	16.38±0.14	12.5±0.13
1929-53349-0372	-	-	0.41±0.22	-	5.49±0.95	0.42±0.13	0.47±0.14	0.18±0.06	0.58±0.07	0.95±0.17	0.45±0.15
1937-53388-0453	-	44.72±7.5	6.46±1.17	2.65±0.93	22.46±1.59	2.36±0.33	-	1.13±0.14	6.67±0.46	4.57±0.67	4.74±0.71
2094-53851-0261	-	297.27±35.83	-	-	-	1.2±0.55	5.47±1.0	5.89±0.97	22.63±0.89	18.05±0.5	15.93±0.5
2124-53770-0272	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2126-53794-0075	3.43±0.86	14.02±0.6	0.44±0.15	2.37±0.08	5.99±0.2	0.45±0.13	-	1.17±0.16	2.86±0.03	1.82±0.12	1.85±0.04
2130-53881-0553	23.74±5.01	185.38±5.91	6.2±1.08	80.01±3.52	246.11±10.29	2.35±0.29	5.38±0.81	7.38±1.91	91.91±2.9	22.81±0.95	18.45±0.9
2132-53493-0224	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2170-53875-0347	-	4.93±0.56	-	-	1.21±0.26	-	-	-	2.03±0.07	0.54±0.17	0.3±0.09
2207-53820-0018	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2234-53823-0120	11.92±2.26	11.87±2.12	-	-	0.81±0.62	0.42±0.19	-	0.55±0.15	4.05±0.12	0.88±0.4	-
2268-53682-0424	1.0±1.02	1.12±1.13	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.7±0.93	0.44±0.31	0.27±0.15
2273-53709-0027	-	-	1.23±0.2	-	-	-	0.97±0.2	1.13±0.17	2.11±0.03	1.75±0.1	1.19±0.05
2275-53705-0378	-	-	0.24±0.04	-	0.18±0.04	-	0.27±0.04	0.12±0.03	0.45±0.03	0.33±0.02	0.18±0.01
2350-53765-0539	-	-	1.13±0.26	-	3.42±1.31	0.8±0.06	2.88±0.45	1.85±0.17	15.95±0.09	5.9±0.12	4.06±0.06
2352-53770-0006	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2426-53795-0583	9.97±1.54	17.03±2.65	-	-	1.4±0.54	-	1.7±0.44	1.04±0.15	7.56±0.1	3.75±0.14	2.6±0.1
2496-54178-0330	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2515-54180-0046	-	-	0.1±0.04	1.84±0.01	5.67±0.08	-	0.34±0.09	0.25±0.04	0.45±0.03	0.64±0.01	0.41±0.0
2518-54243-0066	6.86±1.93	100.9±3.87	2.58±0.58	15.01±0.31	48.99±1.49	-	3.04±0.96	4.53±1.18	62.17±1.01	17.29±0.2	15.22±0.27
2523-54572-0428	-	22.8±1.08	2.17±0.6	-	2.42±0.69	-	1.42±0.28	-	21.17±0.24	6.14±0.05	5.29±0.05
2580-54092-0232	-	-	0.4±0.17	-	0.68±0.19	-	0.23±0.06	0.27±0.1	0.89±0.17	0.61±0.18	0.2±0.08
2599-54234-0571	-	4.54±0.48	-	-	-	-	0.33±0.06	0.24±0.07	0.28±0.01	0.58±0.03	0.37±0.04
2613-54481-0304	1.51±0.75	8.44±0.94	0.28±0.11	1.4±0.07	3.75±0.2	0.57±0.1	0.22±0.11	0.47±0.11	3.1±0.12	1.23±0.04	0.84±0.06
2746-54232-0165	109.85±28.71	189.8±25.56	-	-	7.09±2.82	2.36±0.76	-	3.14±0.53	11.68±0.22	4.78±0.86	2.49±1.05
2764-54535-0355	-	5.0±0.33	-	-	1.2±0.33	-	0.44±0.07	-	1.57±0.05	1.31±0.22	1.34±0.18
2765-54535-0129	-	53.71±3.05	-	-	3.57±1.15	-	2.56±0.43	1.51±0.21	6.59±0.18	6.32±0.19	4.77±0.08
2774-54534-0448	-	22.51±0.96	-	2.48±0.22	6.7±0.38	0.52±0.08	3.22±2.35	1.49±0.44	4.28±0.29	3.76±0.49	2.07±0.21
2776-54554-0098	-	208.23±237.22	-	-	5.07±4.8	1.65±1.42	-	0.21±0.06	4.75±2.9	3.65±2.37	-
2782-54592-0240	0.25±0.13	1.73±0.18	-	-	-	0.15±0.06	0.29±0.04	-	0.59±0.02	0.34±0.01	0.26±0.01
1693-53446-0629	-	1.54±0.19	-	0.1±0.03	0.37±0.11	-	0.39±0.14	-	0.5±0.05	0.49±0.03	0.32±0.05

Notes. (1) Control sample galaxies Plate-Mid-Fiberid information from SDSS DR9 and matched on Table A.2.

Table A.6. Extinction corrected permitted emission lines measurements in the CTR sample.

Object (1)	Av [mag]	H δ flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	H γ flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	H β flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	H α flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	EW H α [Å]
0275-51910-0320	1.3±0.1	2.58±0.11	3.86±0.24	6.2±0.09	17.79±0.16	38.8±0.3
0420-51871-0285	1.2±0.1	0.19±0.02	0.23±0.03	0.43±0.01	1.22±0.03	12.2±0.3
0420-51871-0517	1.3±0.1	1.02±0.05	1.8±0.05	4.09±0.1	11.73±0.14	25.7±0.3
0421-51821-0003	2.3±1.0	-	2.1±1.03	1.35±0.6	3.88±1.23	2.4±0.5
0731-52460-0345	1.5±0.2	1.48±0.32	1.29±0.25	2.06±0.14	5.92±0.09	4.5±0.1
0860-52319-0120	1.2±0.1	1.02±0.16	1.48±0.06	2.87±0.03	8.24±0.15	21.3±0.4
1266-52709-0142	2.2±1.1	-	4.59±2.42	1.11±0.62	3.18±1.07	1.5±0.2
1588-52965-0534	0.8±0.3	0.22±0.03	0.39±0.08	0.56±0.05	1.6±0.03	6.4±0.1
1601-53115-0280	1.0±1.2	0.75±0.52	0.77±0.47	0.45±0.28	1.3±0.5	2.1±0.3
1607-53083-0452	1.7±0.1	12.13±0.57	18.93±0.95	31.87±1.21	91.46±1.16	38.7±0.5
1652-53555-0578	0.1±0.1	0.07±0.04	0.11±0.01	0.37±0.0	1.05±0.01	19.3±0.2
1693-53446-0629	1.2±0.1	0.43±0.12	0.7±0.09	1.29±0.06	3.7±0.04	9.1±0.1
1771-53498-0483	2.1±0.3	7.06±1.43	7.32±1.15	15.23±1.42	43.71±3.27	15.9±1.1
1776-53858-0098	1.2±0.2	0.94±0.12	0.65±0.11	1.01±0.06	2.91±0.04	7.9±0.1
1852-53534-0298	2.5±0.1	24.06±2.7	28.45±1.76	37.19±0.78	106.75±1.28	21.1±0.3
1929-53349-0372	1.6±0.3	1.63±0.54	1.43±0.14	1.83±0.15	5.26±0.1	5.9±0.1
1937-53388-0453	3.2±0.3	11.58±1.86	13.86±1.81	12.56±1.1	36.04±0.83	5.9±0.1
2094-53851-0261	3.4±0.2	-	20.15±3.63	31.01±2.21	89.0±3.35	17.4±0.6
2124-53770-0272	-	-	-	-	-	0.4±0.1
2126-53794-0075	1.4±0.1	-	-	1.21±0.03	3.46±0.04	2.1±0.0
2130-53881-0553	2.0±0.2	16.02±0.76	23.83±0.79	36.83±2.26	105.7±2.22	19.9±0.4
2132-53493-0224	-	-	-	-	-	2.3±0.8
2170-53875-0347	1.2±0.3	0.55±0.14	0.23±0.13	0.96±0.09	2.76±0.08	2.9±0.1
2227-53820-0018	-	-	-	-	-	0.3±0.1
2234-53823-0120	1.6±0.3	3.05±0.53	2.22±0.21	2.79±0.28	8.01±0.2	4.5±0.1
2268-53682-0424	1.7±1.5	0.86±0.88	0.87±0.8	0.68±0.57	1.95±1.1	2.6±0.6
2273-53709-0027	1.0±0.1	2.12±0.3	1.69±0.02	2.21±0.03	6.36±0.11	11.0±0.2
2277-53705-0378	0.8±0.1	0.18±0.09	0.25±0.06	0.43±0.01	1.24±0.03	5.5±0.1
2350-53765-0539	1.5±0.1	8.18±1.22	8.68±0.56	12.66±0.4	36.35±0.5	12.5±0.2
2352-53770-0006	-	-	-	-	-	0.8±0.2
2426-53795-0583	1.9±0.1	2.69±0.35	4.66±0.08	7.44±0.23	21.36±0.19	21.0±0.2
2496-54178-0330	-	-	-	-	-	0.4±0.0
2515-54180-0046	0.0±0.1	0.56±0.06	0.93±0.01	1.77±0.02	5.09±0.07	48.9±0.7
2518-54243-0066	2.1±0.1	10.64±0.28	17.24±0.56	32.11±0.4	92.15±0.99	40.0±0.4
2523-54572-0428	2.1±0.1	5.97±0.39	9.63±0.4	17.57±0.37	50.42±0.45	30.8±0.3
2580-54092-0232	1.0±0.9	1.02±0.39	0.9±0.4	0.57±0.21	1.64±0.33	3.2±0.3
2599-54234-0571	0.9±0.2	0.31±0.04	0.47±0.04	0.8±0.04	2.29±0.03	5.6±0.1
2613-54481-0304	1.6±0.3	0.46±0.26	0.61±0.07	0.81±0.09	2.33±0.09	2.7±0.1
2746-54232-0165	3.4±0.3	10.48±3.74	7.61±1.2	4.16±0.38	11.95±0.22	2.0±0.0
2764-54535-0355	1.8±0.3	1.18±0.14	2.09±0.16	2.59±0.29	7.44±0.2	7.8±0.1
2765-54535-0129	2.6±0.1	8.41±1.55	10.2±1.5	13.67±0.49	39.23±0.24	16.7±0.1
2774-54534-0448	1.4±0.3	1.05±0.45	1.71±0.18	1.88±0.15	5.41±0.16	2.0±0.0
2776-54554-0098	3.5±1.6	12.29±13.48	5.47±6.5	4.82±4.79	13.83±8.44	2.3±0.2
2782-54592-0240	0.6±0.3	0.24±0.03	0.26±0.03	0.58±0.05	1.66±0.05	7.1±0.2
1693-53446-0629	1.2±0.1	0.43±0.12	0.7±0.09	1.29±0.06	3.7±0.04	9.1±0.1

Notes. (1) Control sample galaxies Plate-MJD-Fiberid information from SDSS DR9 and matched on Table A.2.

Table A.7. Classification of each galaxy from the INT sample using BPTs and WHAN diagrams, and the one obtained when we required the same classification in at least four out of the five diagrams.

Object (1)	[NII] BPT	[SII] BPT	[OI] BPT	[OII] BPT	WHAN	4/5 DGs
AM0012-235 A	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM0012-235 B	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM0103-520 A	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM0103-520 B	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM0302-611 G1	LINER	-	-	-	wAGN	INC
AM0302-611 G2	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM0302-611 G3	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM0302-611 G4	Seyfert	LINER	-	-	RG	INC
AM0338-320 A	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM0338-320 B	Seyfert	Seyfert	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM0348-502 G1	LINER	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	sAGN	AGN
AM0348-502 G2	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM0348-502 G3	SF	SF	-	-	SF	INC
AM0737-764 A	LINER	LINER	LINER	SF	wAGN	AGN
AM0737-764 B	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM0830-235 A	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM0830-235 B	Seyfert	-	Seyfert	LINER	RG	INC
AM1058-243 A	SF	SF	LINER	LINER	sAGN	INC
AM1058-243 B	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM1125-374 A	Composite	SF	Seyfert	SF	wAGN	INC
AM1125-374 B	Composite	SF	SF	SF	wAGN	INC
AM1132-450 A	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM1132-450 B	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM1228-260 A	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
AM1228-260 B	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM1238-340 A	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM1238-340 B	Composite	LINER	LINER	SF	wAGN	AGN
AM1411-434 A	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM1411-434 B	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM1445-274 G1	Seyfert	LINER	LINER	LINER	sAGN	AGN
AM1445-274 G2	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM1722-595 A	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
AM1722-595 B	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM1933-422 A	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
AM1933-422 B	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	SF	sAGN	AGN
AM1933-422 C	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM1941-564 A	Composite	SF	-	-	sAGN	INC
AM1941-564 B	Seyfert	LINER	-	-	RG	INC
AM2004-662 G1	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
AM2004-662 G3	LINER	LINER	-	-	RG	INC
AM2036-510 G1	Composite	LINER	Seyfert	LINER	wAGN	AGN
AM2036-510 G2	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2036-510 G3	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2106-624 G2	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM2108-452 G1	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
AM2108-452 G2	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
AM2108-452 G3	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2117-515 G1	LINER	SF	Seyfert	SF	wAGN	INC
AM2117-515 G2	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2117-515 G4	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2117-515 G5	SF	Seyfert	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2117-515 G6	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2117-515 KNOTS	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2132-664 G1	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM2132-664 G3	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2217-490 G1	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
AM2217-490 G2	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
AM2220-493 G1	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	sAGN	AGN
AM2220-493 G2	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	sAGN	AGN

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog and [Table A.1](#).

Table A.8. Classification of each galaxy from the CTR sample using BPTs and WHAN diagrams, and the one obtained when we required the same classification in at least four out of the five diagrams.

Plate-MJd-Fiberid (1)	[NII] BPT	[SII] BPT	[OI] BPT	[OII] BPT	WHAN	4/5 DGs
0275-51910-0320	SF	SF	SF	-	SF	SF
0420-51871-0285	SF	LINER	-	-	SF	INC
0420-51871-0517	SF	SF	-	-	SF	INC
0421-51821-0003	Composite	SF	-	-	RG	INC
0731-52460-0345	Seyfert	LINER	Seyfert	SF	wAGN	AGN
0860-52319-0120	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
1266-52709-0142	Seyfert	LINER	-	-	RG	INC
1588-52965-0534	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
1601-53115-0280	Composite	-	LINER	SF	RG	INC
1607-53083-0452	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
1652-53555-0578	SF	SF	Seyfert	SF	SF	SF
1693-53446-0629	SF	SF	-	-	sAGN	INC
1771-53498-0483	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
1776-53858-0098	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
1852-53534-0298	SF	SF	SF	-	sAGN	INC
1929-53349-0372	-	-	-	-	SF	INC
1937-53388-0453	Composite	SF	SF	SF	wAGN	INC
2094-53851-0261	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
2124-53770-0272	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
2126-53794-0075	Seyfert	LINER	-	-	RG	INC
2130-53881-0553	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	Seyfert	sAGN	AGN
2132-53493-0224	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
2170-53875-0347	Composite	SF	-	-	RG	INC
2227-53820-0018	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
2234-53823-0120	-	-	-	-	wAGN	INC
2268-53682-0424	LINER	SF	-	-	RG	INC
2273-53709-0027	-	-	-	-	SF	INC
2277-53705-0378	SF	SF	LINER	-	SF	INC
2350-53765-0539	SF	SF	SF	-	sAGN	INC
2352-53770-0006	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
2426-53795-0583	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF
2496-54178-0330	-	-	-	-	RG	INC
2515-54180-0046	SF	SF	Seyfert	-	SF	INC
2518-54243-0066	Composite	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	INC
2523-54572-0428	SF	SF	-	-	sAGN	INC
2580-54092-0232	Composite	SF	LINER	-	wAGN	INC
2599-54234-0571	-	-	-	-	wAGN	INC
2613-54481-0304	LINER	Seyfert	Seyfert	LINER	RG	AGN
2746-54232-0165	LINER	LINER	SF	SF	RG	INC
2764-54535-0355	Composite	SF	-	-	sAGN	INC
2765-54535-0129	SF	SF	SF	SF	sAGN	SF
2774-54534-0448	LINER	LINER	SF	LINER	RG	RG
2776-54554-0098	Composite	-	-	-	RG	INC
2782-54592-0240	-	-	-	-	SF	INC
1693-53446-0629	SF	SF	-	-	sAGN	INC

Notes. (1) Control sample galaxies Plate-MJd-Fiberid information from SDSS DR9 and matched on Table A.2.

Appendix B: Excluded sources additional material

This appendix presents the information on the excluded sources from the initial interacting candidates sample of Table A.1. They were excluded for not being part of an interacting system or if there was insufficient information to confirm or discard their nature. The images and spectra of the galaxies are in Figs B.1 and B.2. Table B.1 presents their radial velocities and the reason why they were excluded. Finally, their forbidden and permitted emission line fluxes are shown in Tables B.2 and B.3, respectively.

Fig. B.1. Same as in Fig. 1, but for the galaxies discarded as real pairs or groups.

Fig. B.1. continue.

Fig. B.2. continued.

Fig. B.2. continued.

Table B.1. Nonphysical, uncertain, or unobserved systems radial velocities (when available) and additional information.

System name (1)	Radial velocity [km/s] (2)	Comments
AM 0103-520 C	18576 ± 58	Not make part of the system.
AM 0237-525 A	16460 ± 57	
B		Without a good S/N spectrum.
AM 0305-824 A	4514 ± 105	Only this galaxy observed.
AM 0908-674 G1 (A)	1546 ± 126	Possible companion (not observed) toward the northeast.
B		It is a star toward the southeast of A.
AM 0952-273 A	4352 ± 86	It is not a pair.
B	19336 ± 88	
AM 1026-442 G1	2427 ± 75	Primary is NGC 3261. Two objects to the south were not observed.
AM 1438-400 G1	7684 ± 91	It is not a pair.
G2	14924 ± 86	
AM 2004-662 G2	27853 ± 84	It is a foreground galaxy.
G4	27977 ± 102	It is a foreground galaxy.
AM 2024-525 G1	4769 ± 82	Not make part of the system.
G2	15958 ± 106	Despite the redshifts, there are no signs of interaction and the galaxies are far apart.
G3	15924 ± 101	
G4	16061 ± 188	-
AM 2031-500 A	2433 ± 55	It is not a pair. A looks like a double or triple nucleus.
B	4488 ± 71	
AM 2037-550 A	11366 ± 68	We do not have a spectrum.
B		
AM 2038-323 G1 (A)	5566 ± 96	It is not a pair.
G2 (B)	36821 ± 123	
AM 2057-650 G1 (A)	13517 ± 94	
G2 (B)	13869 ± 97	B has faint continuum and no emission lines. Redshift is uncertain. The possible companion is at 36 arcsec north of A.
AM 2100-503 G1 (A)	4901 ± 107	It is not a group.
G2 (B)	15037 ± 87	
G3 (C)	$59459 \pm -$	
AM 2117-371 G1 (A)	15185 ± 83	It is not a pair.
G2 (B)	31066 ± 83	
AM 2117-515 G3		The slit does not go through the nucleus.
AM 2117-682 G1	25960 ± 81	It is not a group with G3.
G2	-	Close to G1. Not observed.
G3	16922 ± 94	
AM 2132-664 G2		Star toward the south of G1.
AM 2137-515 A	16899 ± 90	Not part of the pair.
B	24729 ± 95	B is likely a pair, no spectrum available.
AM 2147-544 G1 (A)	8614 ± 86	It is not a pair.
G2 - B	15747 ± 89	
AM 2220-661 A	10513 ± 109	It is not a pair. A spiral + star.
AM 2246-490 G1 (A)	$12684 \pm -$	Redshift is uncertain. The Ha+NII is inside the CCD gap in both spectra.
G2 (B)	$12894 \pm -$	-

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog and [Table A.1](#). (2) Systemic velocity obtained following the method described in [Sect. 2.1](#)

Table B.2. Extinction corrected emission lines measurements for forbidden and helium transitions of the excluded galaxies.

Object	[O II] λ 3726 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[O II] λ 3729 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[O III] λ 4363 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[O III] λ 4959 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[O III] λ 5007 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[N II] λ 5755 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	He I λ 5876 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[O I] λ 6300 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[N II] λ 6548 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[N II] λ 6583 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[S II] λ 6716 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]	[S II] λ 6731 flux $\times 10^{-15}$ [$\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]
AM0103-520 C	32.96 $\pm$ 19.95	13.66 $\pm$ 8.41	-	-	2.85 $\pm$ 1.27	-	-	-	1.84 $\pm$ 0.6	2.57 $\pm$ 0.83	1.7 $\pm$ 0.57	1.6 $\pm$ 0.51
AM0237-525 A	14.21 $\pm$ 0.82	14.21 $\pm$ 0.82	0.04 $\pm$ 0.02	0.36 $\pm$ 0.03	1.31 $\pm$ 0.07	-	0.52 $\pm$ 0.02	0.21 $\pm$ 0.01	2.46 $\pm$ 0.02	8.9 $\pm$ 0.11	2.98 $\pm$ 0.14	1.83 $\pm$ 0.18
AM0305-824 A	2.52 $\pm$ 0.04	2.73 $\pm$ 0.05	-	0.61 $\pm$ 0.01	1.88 $\pm$ 0.02	0.01 $\pm$ 0.0	0.05 $\pm$ 0.01	0.08 $\pm$ 0.01	-	0.21 $\pm$ 0.01	0.48 $\pm$ 0.03	0.28 $\pm$ 0.02
AM0908-674 G1	770.12 $\pm$ 184.0	973.48 $\pm$ 179.4	-	26.57 $\pm$ 2.2	149.64 $\pm$ 9.19	5.3 $\pm$ 1.49	38.5 $\pm$ 4.92	-	172.56 $\pm$ 9.56	637.24 $\pm$ 4.38	395.49 $\pm$ 5.64	315.31 $\pm$ 6.18
AM0952-273 A	9.84 $\pm$ 0.26	3.6 $\pm$ 0.28	0.24 $\pm$ 0.04	2.98 $\pm$ 0.03	9.14 $\pm$ 0.09	0.04 $\pm$ 0.0	0.24 $\pm$ 0.02	0.2 $\pm$ 0.01	-	0.52 $\pm$ 0.01	0.87 $\pm$ 0.02	0.54 $\pm$ 0.05
AM0952-273 B	367.42 $\pm$ 85.53	417.4 $\pm$ 89.53	51.04 $\pm$ 25.12	2.37 $\pm$ 0.84	41.07 $\pm$ 3.25	6.03 $\pm$ 0.88	11.25 $\pm$ 1.21	7.51 $\pm$ 0.82	35.15 $\pm$ 1.77	47.41 $\pm$ 4.09	30.83 $\pm$ 1.86	-
AM1026-442 G1	83.18 $\pm$ 11.03	25.86 $\pm$ 9.24	-	6.28 $\pm$ 0.82	23.07 $\pm$ 2.03	5.12 $\pm$ 0.8	-	-	61.56 $\pm$ 3.11	135.85 $\pm$ 6.75	46.03 $\pm$ 2.1	48.52 $\pm$ 2.68
AM1438-400 G1	17.9 $\pm$ 1.45	5.8 $\pm$ 1.16	-	0.76 $\pm$ 0.12	0.83 $\pm$ 0.12	-	1.6 $\pm$ 0.11	-	6.79 $\pm$ 0.34	20.85 $\pm$ 0.18	2.93 $\pm$ 0.34	5.0 $\pm$ 0.19
AM1438-400 G2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AM2004-662 G2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AM2024-525 G1	208.77 $\pm$ 7.22	116.19 $\pm$ 9.8	-	5.96 $\pm$ 0.14	22.43 $\pm$ 0.98	1.2 $\pm$ 0.14	4.48 $\pm$ 0.3	4.28 $\pm$ 0.22	10.55 $\pm$ 0.48	37.12 $\pm$ 0.25	31.64 $\pm$ 0.39	20.79 $\pm$ 0.29
AM2024-525 G2	90.25 $\pm$ 1.98	84.82 $\pm$ 2.21	-	6.45 $\pm$ 0.19	21.71 $\pm$ 0.22	0.82 $\pm$ 0.2	4.33 $\pm$ 0.2	2.46 $\pm$ 0.14	18.0 $\pm$ 0.31	66.98 $\pm$ 0.58	17.14 $\pm$ 0.2	12.97 $\pm$ 0.21
AM2024-525 G3	5.56 $\pm$ 0.21	6.73 $\pm$ 0.26	-	0.69 $\pm$ 0.04	1.48 $\pm$ 0.06	-	0.34 $\pm$ 0.05	0.18 $\pm$ 0.0	0.58 $\pm$ 0.07	3.45 $\pm$ 0.07	2.17 $\pm$ 0.04	1.86 $\pm$ 0.03
AM2024-525 G4	6.0 $\pm$ 0.16	6.21 $\pm$ 0.16	-	0.48 $\pm$ 0.07	1.44 $\pm$ 0.04	0.05 $\pm$ 0.01	0.14 $\pm$ 0.02	0.12 $\pm$ 0.01	0.14 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	1.06 $\pm$ 0.02	0.73 $\pm$ 0.02
AM2031-500 A	36.54 $\pm$ 1.34	43.32 $\pm$ 1.18	-	5.04 $\pm$ 0.07	15.43 $\pm$ 0.23	0.12 $\pm$ 0.02	1.51 $\pm$ 0.12	0.61 $\pm$ 0.07	3.01 $\pm$ 0.25	8.94 $\pm$ 0.16	9.06 $\pm$ 0.19	7.12 $\pm$ 0.19
AM2031-500 B	76.2 $\pm$ 1.96	59.68 $\pm$ 1.62	-	2.89 $\pm$ 0.13	13.75 $\pm$ 0.64	1.98 $\pm$ 0.12	3.37 $\pm$ 0.26	0.72 $\pm$ 0.22	13.38 $\pm$ 0.71	44.21 $\pm$ 0.49	22.29 $\pm$ 0.41	14.59 $\pm$ 0.49
AM2037-550 A	105.86 $\pm$ 2.02	81.93 $\pm$ 2.04	-	37.02 $\pm$ 0.35	112.38 $\pm$ 1.05	0.2 $\pm$ 0.01	4.42 $\pm$ 0.16	1.38 $\pm$ 0.07	2.92 $\pm$ 0.81	15.27 $\pm$ 0.13	12.15 $\pm$ 0.07	8.45 $\pm$ 0.06
AM2038-323 G1	30.18 $\pm$ 3.76	-	-	4.01 $\pm$ 0.26	14.12 $\pm$ 0.99	3.02 $\pm$ 0.23	1.6 $\pm$ 0.11	0.64 $\pm$ 0.04	12.97 $\pm$ 0.23	34.33 $\pm$ 0.32	11.28 $\pm$ 0.3	9.66 $\pm$ 0.3
AM2038-323 G2	1.62 $\pm$ 0.19	0.93 $\pm$ 0.09	-	0.69 $\pm$ 0.07	0.27 $\pm$ 0.04	-	0.05 $\pm$ 0.01	0.2 $\pm$ 0.02	0.3 $\pm$ 0.01	0.95 $\pm$ 0.02	0.58 $\pm$ 0.03	0.08 $\pm$ 0.02
AM2057-650 G1	2.88 $\pm$ 0.64	4.04 $\pm$ 0.69	-	1.73 $\pm$ 0.18	3.16 $\pm$ 0.25	-	-	0.06 $\pm$ 0.01	2.11 $\pm$ 0.17	-	2.55 $\pm$ 0.25	3.18 $\pm$ 0.2
AM2057-650 G2	0.09 $\pm$ 0.02	0.06 $\pm$ 0.01	-	0.02 $\pm$ 0.0	0.03 $\pm$ 0.0	-	-	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0	0.03 $\pm$ 0.0	0.02 $\pm$ 0.0	0.06 $\pm$ 0.01	0.08 $\pm$ 0.01
AM2100-503 G1	121.63 $\pm$ 2.3	19.63 $\pm$ 2.22	-	1.8 $\pm$ 0.12	11.51 $\pm$ 0.49	1.3 $\pm$ 0.1	2.74 $\pm$ 0.15	0.98 $\pm$ 0.1	7.75 $\pm$ 0.6	29.37 $\pm$ 0.23	17.7 $\pm$ 0.24	12.28 $\pm$ 0.28
AM2100-503 G2	0.15 $\pm$ 0.01	0.12 $\pm$ 0.01	-	0.06 $\pm$ 0.0	0.09 $\pm$ 0.01	0.02 $\pm$ 0.0	0.02 $\pm$ 0.0	0.03 $\pm$ 0.0	-	0.82 $\pm$ 0.04	0.29 $\pm$ 0.01	0.36 $\pm$ 0.01
AM2117-371 G1	38.13 $\pm$ 3.47	-	-	1.66 $\pm$ 0.21	2.75 $\pm$ 0.09	0.7 $\pm$ 0.11	0.34 $\pm$ 0.06	-	-	6.57 $\pm$ 0.21	3.57 $\pm$ 0.2	3.85 $\pm$ 0.13
AM2117-371 G2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AM2117-682 G1	160.69 $\pm$ 35.26	202.01 $\pm$ 35.47	-	18.23 $\pm$ 1.49	21.15 $\pm$ 2.13	-	-	0.54 $\pm$ 0.1	9.52 $\pm$ 0.71	18.69 $\pm$ 1.35	1.15 $\pm$ 0.32	3.69 $\pm$ 0.71
AM2117-682 G3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AM2137-515 A	3.66 $\pm$ 0.44	1.34 $\pm$ 0.4	-	0.4 $\pm$ 0.05	0.65 $\pm$ 0.06	-	-	0.25 $\pm$ 0.02	0.69 $\pm$ 0.08	1.89 $\pm$ 0.13	0.73 $\pm$ 0.06	0.81 $\pm$ 0.07
AM2137-515 B	33.5 $\pm$ 1.05	42.03 $\pm$ 0.72	0.31 $\pm$ 0.12	1.93 $\pm$ 0.07	4.83 $\pm$ 0.16	-	1.01 $\pm$ 0.03	1.35 $\pm$ 0.06	3.21 $\pm$ 0.06	8.92 $\pm$ 0.07	4.43 $\pm$ 0.06	3.65 $\pm$ 0.05
AM2147-544 G1	-	21.57 $\pm$ 5.76	-	0.91 $\pm$ 0.09	4.61 $\pm$ 0.45	0.25 $\pm$ 0.07	0.92 $\pm$ 0.08	-	4.19 $\pm$ 0.26	13.22 $\pm$ 0.37	1.01 $\pm$ 0.25	2.77 $\pm$ 0.08
AM2147-544 G2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AM2220-661	11.75 $\pm$ 1.45	3.3 $\pm$ 1.56	-	0.15 $\pm$ 0.02	1.79 $\pm$ 0.09	0.25 $\pm$ 0.05	0.52 $\pm$ 0.03	-	4.49 $\pm$ 0.15	11.56 $\pm$ 0.08	2.86 $\pm$ 0.15	3.05 $\pm$ 0.15
AM2246-490 G1	34.18 $\pm$ 6.93	57.21 $\pm$ 6.9	-	37.27 $\pm$ 2.15	32.39 $\pm$ 2.08	4.26 $\pm$ 0.49	-	7.26 $\pm$ 1.75	312.25 $\pm$ 12.41	424.09 $\pm$ 21.63	16.92 $\pm$ 1.29	80.68 $\pm$ 2.46

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog and [Table A.1](#).

Table B.3. Extinction corrected permitted emission lines measurements of the excluded galaxies.

Object (1)	Av [mag]	H δ	H γ	H β	H α	EW H α [Å]
		flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	flux x 10 ⁻¹⁵ [erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²]	
AM0103-520 C	5.5±1.2	10.13±5.75	4.62±2.61	0.88±0.5	2.52±0.85	0.9±0.1
AM0237-525 A	3.0±0.1	2.73±0.31	3.55±0.27	6.09±0.27	17.47±0.12	58.1±0.3
AM0305-824 A	0.0±0.1	0.33±0.03	0.44±0.02	0.74±0.02	2.11±0.03	48.0±0.6
AM0908-674 G1	4.4±0.1	156.15±3.4	244.24±24.14	640.7±21.13	1838.8±10.71	28.1±0.1
AM0952-273 A	1.5±0.1	0.55±0.06	1.25±0.05	2.53±0.1	7.25±0.05	68.3±0.4
AM0952-273 B	7.4±0.4	-	203.76±26.33	20.38±2.92	58.5±4.27	2.9±0.2
AM1026-442 G1	2.8±0.4	44.01±3.7	-	12.67±1.76	36.35±2.47	1.1±0.1
AM1438-400 G1	2.7±0.1	4.59±1.03	9.54±1.01	19.83±0.78	56.92±0.34	24.0±0.1
AM1438-400 G2	-	-	-	-	-	0.0±0.0
AM2004-662 G2	-	-	-	-	-	0.0±0.0
AM2024-525 G1	4.0±0.1	22.09±0.64	21.02±0.47	43.13±1.39	123.79±0.89	31.1±0.2
AM2024-525 G2	4.2±0.1	15.07±0.39	20.0±1.47	42.59±2.03	122.24±0.9	76.1±0.4
AM2024-525 G3	2.0±0.2	-	1.4±0.18	3.58±0.29	10.26±0.16	31.3±0.2
AM2024-525 G4	2.3±0.2	0.23±0.05	0.53±0.07	1.38±0.1	3.95±0.05	30.9±0.2
AM2031-500 A	1.6±0.2	4.61±0.62	5.2±0.21	12.24±0.61	35.11±0.25	20.6±0.1
AM2031-500 B	2.6±0.1	12.21±0.79	21.99±0.67	43.19±1.84	123.94±0.99	36.2±0.2
AM2037-550 A	2.0±0.1	12.1±0.8	19.25±0.8	43.45±1.45	124.69±0.75	240.5±1.3
AM2038-323 G1	2.7±0.1	8.45±0.8	7.04±0.24	18.31±0.65	52.54±0.48	10.4±0.1
AM2038-323 G2	2.7±0.3	0.46±0.11	0.53±0.07	0.81±0.07	2.33±0.04	26.9±0.2
AM2057-650 G1	2.0±0.3	-	-	1.18±0.1	3.38±0.18	1.3±0.1
AM2057-650 G2	0.2±0.5	-	-	0.02±0.0	0.06±0.01	1.1±0.1
AM2100-503 G1	2.7±0.1	11.7±0.4	11.85±0.52	30.8±1.15	88.41±0.53	30.5±0.2
AM2100-503 G2	0.0±0.3	-	-	0.04±0.0	0.11±0.01	0.7±0.1
AM2117-371 G1	2.9±0.2	-	-	6.87±0.51	19.71±0.28	10.6±0.1
AM2117-371 G2	-	-	-	-	-	0.3±0.0
AM2117-682 G1	6.0±0.4	-	-	5.32±0.6	15.27±1.02	1.7±0.1
AM2117-682 G3	-	-	-	-	-	0.4±0.1
AM2137-515 A	2.6±0.4	0.37±0.06	0.58±0.07	0.34±0.04	0.98±0.07	1.1±0.1
AM2137-515 B	4.5±0.1	1.47±0.56	6.29±0.59	6.82±0.25	19.58±0.14	30.6±0.2
AM2147-544 G1	3.5±0.1	5.35±0.17	1.77±0.88	14.63±0.57	41.99±0.25	12.0±0.1
AM2147-544 G2	-	-	-	-	-	0.0±0.0
AM2220-661	2.9±0.1	1.96±0.35	4.06±0.12	7.2±0.32	20.67±0.23	13.2±0.1
AM2246-490 G1	3.4±0.2	-	7.7±1.07	48.26±3.33	138.5±4.44	20.0±0.6

Notes. (1) System name and component according to [Arp & Madore \(1987\)](#) catalog and [Table A.1](#).